
STRUCTURAL AND CAPITAL EMPLOYED EFFICIENCY AND FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF LISTED CONSUMER GOODS COMPANIES IN NIGERIA

Nasiru Rabi^{*1}, Joshua Okpanachi^{*2}, Onipe Adabenege Yahaya^{*3}, Adzor Ibiameke^{*4}

^{*1,2,3,4}Nigerian Defence Academy Kaduna, Nigeria.

DOI: <https://www.doi.org/10.56726/IRJMETS73227>

ABSTRACT

The improvement of profitability to achieve financial growth is driven by technological implementation, process improvement, and optimal capital structure. This study investigates the effect of structural and capital-employed efficiency on the financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. An ex-post facto research design was used on the panel data utilizing purposive sampling techniques to select a sample size of twelve (12) from a population of twenty-one (21) listed consumer goods in Nigeria. The study covered the period from 2013 to 2023 and employed multiple regression techniques using STATA 13 software. The results reveal that structural capital and capital-employed efficiency positively and significantly affect financial performance. This study concludes that structural and capital-employed efficiencies significantly affect the financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria. The study, therefore, recommends that firms should work to maximize their structural capital by developing internal processes and exploiting organizational knowledge. Firms should also establish strong financial management through optimal capital structure to improve their capital investment efficiency.

Keywords: Capital Employed Efficiency, Financial Performance, Profitability, Structural Capital Employed.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every manufacturing sector seeks growth and financial success which are usually measured by sales volume, profit, and market share. However, attaining this growth and effectively leveraging opportunities for development and change depends on how well structural and capital resources are being organized, managed and converted into shareholder value.

For many years, researchers have proclaimed that there is a connection between a business firm's performance and the efficient use of factors of production such as land, labour, and capital resources. Firms that manage to capture a sustainable competitive advantage tend to be more successful in adding value when they use these production factors efficiently. Thus, financial performance is widely recognised as an indicator of a company's success and can be assessed by examining their annual financial statements much like their counterparts worldwide.

Previous studies have indicated that manufacturing firms in Nigeria are still lagging in growth potential and competitiveness. One significant obstacle to the sustainable growth of the manufacturing industry in Nigeria is the lack of access to financing. Many manufacturing companies struggle to secure the necessary funds for expansion, technology upgrades, and routine maintenance. This financial shortfall threatens their growth potential and disrupts their day-to-day operations. This is because. High interest rates, collateral requirements, and a lack of credit facilities significantly constrain business expansion and investment.

In addition to financial challenges, the manufacturing industry in Nigeria is engulfed with inadequate power supply and deficiencies in transportation logistics. These issues lead to supply chain disruptions and hinder the production processes. Furthermore, manufacturing firms in Nigeria face uncertainties due to frequent changes in government policies, including taxation, trade regulations, and economic policies. These inconsistencies obstruct firms' long-term strategic planning and investment decisions. Consequently, improving financial performance has become a considerable challenge for some publicly listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

To overcome some challenges, the government has been given support in terms of forex subsidies and other interventions to help the ailing industry. Additionally, in the past, studies were carried out to unravel the problems around the consistent stagnation of the manufacturing sector and possible recommendations to assist in overcoming such challenges. Previous studies were, however, centred around the traditional approach, which this study considers as a gap and comes up to fill. Consequently, the study examined the effect of

structural and capital-employed efficiency on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Structural Capital refers to the entire system within an organization, which includes the organizational structure and culture that upholds the principles and business objectives of the company and also contributes to its overall effectiveness, efficiency, and competitiveness. Unlike physical or financial assets, structural capital is comprised of non-physical elements, often rooted in the organization's systems, processes, culture, and knowledge base. It represents the infrastructure and intellectual resources that support the organization's operations and enable it to create value.

Capital employed on the other hand refers to the total sum of the amount invested in the company. It represents the equity and debt injected into the company for a day-to-day operation. Efficiency also refers to how well a company's resources, including its assets, workforce, and technology, are organized and utilized to achieve its goals. It is the combination of both tangible and intangible assets and thus, efficiency focuses on how effectively a company utilizes its capital (both equity and debt) to generate profits.

It is the assumption of the study that to enhance the financial performance of the manufacturing firms in Nigeria, the combined effect of structural and capital-employed efficiency can create a synergistic impact on financial performance and so, it is therefore imperative to consider the appropriate structure and capital employed efficiency (Abdirahman & Tarique, 2020).

The transition to a knowledge-based economy relies heavily on the significant value of intangible assets. Intellectual assets such as patents, copyrights, and trademarks, which provide competitive advantages, are now better protected than ever. Additionally, the shared values, beliefs, and practices that shape an organization's work environment, along with well-defined and documented processes governing operations to ensure consistency, have been explored as ways to enhance a firm's financial performance.

A company with strong performance indicators is likely to attract more potential investors, suggesting a healthy profitable company. This is because the profitability of companies not only influences stakeholders' perceptions of good performance but also serves as a predictor of shareholder wealth (Elisabeth and Fabienne, 2019; Olaoye and Adesina, 2022). In the today's business environment, a company that prioritizes investment in tangible assets over intangible assets may experience bad management, corruption and even theft. However, since the landscape of the business has changed, it means more investment into intangible assets will support better financial return. While there is no definitive method for quantifying intangible assets, various models have been developed to support their recognition and reporting (Jarrett, 2019).

This study provided answers to the following questions:

1. How does structural capital efficiency affect the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria?
2. How does capital-employed efficiency affect the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria?

To support in providing the answers of the above questions, the following objectives are stated to be measured.

1. Examine the effect of structural capital efficiency on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.
2. Assess the effect of capital employed efficiency on the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

To achieve the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are stated in null form:

H₀₁: Structural capital efficiency does not significantly affect the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Capital employed efficiency does not significantly affect the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The objectives of the study are motivated around providing insights into how effective use of capital and organizational structure affects financial performance, identifying the key drivers of efficiency in Nigerian consumer goods companies, and ultimately offering recommendations for improving performance in the sector. The consumer goods industry is one of the most vital sectors in any economy, particularly in a developing market like Nigeria. Understanding how efficiency in capital utilization and organizational structure affects performance can provide critical insights into the sector's ability to maintain growth, profitability, and competitiveness.

The section that follows section one is the literature review, which provides empirical analyses from various scholars on structural and capital-employed efficiency. It explores concepts such as financial performance, structural capital efficiency, and capital employed efficiency as utilized in the study. Additionally, the chapter delves into relevant empirical studies that are conceptually similar.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The financial performance of a company is an important metric that shows the well-being of a company, which is typically assessed through various financial ratios. These ratios help interpret the numbers presented in financial statements. According to Zangouinezhad and Moshabaki (2009), a strong financial performance indicates that a company is generating profit relative to its revenue, assets, and expenses over a specific period. Thus, to evaluate a company's financial health, effective tools and methodologies are crucial. It is against this background that Helin et al. (2018) highlight that the prominent and widely used financial ratios may include the net profit margin, gross profit margin, coverage ratio, current ratio, quick ratio, return on assets, return on equity, inventory turnover, total assets turnover, and debt-to-equity ratio. These metrics serve as key indicators to gauge a company's financial status.

Abdirahman and Tarique (2020) assert that financial performance refers to the ability of a company to generate earnings and create value for its stakeholders. This indicates that "financial performance" describes a company's capability to produce profit over a specific period. Financial ratios are utilized to assess how well a business operates over time. Consequently, various financial indicators that measure a firm's efficiency demonstrate its ability to convert assets into profits.

This study utilized Return on Assets (ROA) as a measure of financial performance, which serves as an indicator of efficient or inefficient resource management. This metric can signal either positive or negative developments for the company (Castro et al., 2021). Investors are consistently interested in a company's growth; their focus on the operational performance of financial metrics reflects the company's capacity to sustain and enhance value creation. Typically, investors tend to favour firms that consistently show positive financial performance through effective management of resources and capital efficiency. Strong financial performance not only promotes operational competencies and fosters employee innovation but also enhances productivity, leading to competitive advantage and increased firm value (Al-Omouh et al., 2022).

Structural Capital Efficiency

Structural capital is a vital asset for organizations, consisting of non-human resources such as systems, programs, research and development, and intellectual property rights. According to Zangouinezhad and Moshabaki (2009), structural capital efficiency significantly enhances a company's operational performance, fosters innovation among employees, increases productivity, and ultimately contributes to the company's competitive advantage and higher firm value. Equally, Sardo, Serrasqueiro and Alves (2018) contend that structural capital efficiency supports the achievement of the organization's goals and objectives, thereby enhancing financial performance. It involves organizational processes, procedures, technologies, information resources, and intellectual property rights, serving as the foundation for human capital (Xu & Wang, 2019).

Okoye and Okerekeoti (2021) define structural capital efficiency as the effective management, utilization, and preservation of a company's intellectual property and knowledge to improve overall organizational performance. This encompasses intangible assets like trademarks, patents, licenses, technology, and company policies, processes, and procedures, contributing to the organization's ability to operate more efficiently and create sustainable value. Al-Omouh et al. (2022) also emphasize that effective management of structural capital can lead to improved competencies within the organization, inspire innovation among staff, and ultimately lead to higher productivity and increased competitive advantage.

Therefore, organizations with strong structural capital will have a supportive culture that allows their employees to experiment, learn, and implement new ideas. Hence, the focus on structural capital efficiency is crucial for companies to enhance overall performance and create sustainable value for stakeholders. Structural capital continues to benefit the organization even after employees leave. The acquisition and preservation of the company's expertise result in structural capital, represented by intangible assets such as trademarks,

licenses, and patents. Ultimately, structural capital aids the company's human and other capital resources to function more efficiently by providing support.

Capital Employed Efficiency

Capital employed efficiency refers to how effectively a company utilizes its capital to generate profits. This metric is essential for assessing the overall financial performance of a company, as it indicates the organization's ability to produce profit from its capital investments. According to Alavi and Leidner (2001), capital-employed efficiency significantly influences a company's financial performance since it reflects the effective use of both tangible and intangible assets. This indicates the company's capability to generate returns on its total capital employed.

Additionally, Andreeva and Garanina (2016) emphasized that capital-employed efficiency is vital for evaluating a company's ability to convert its capital into profits. It demonstrates the efficiency and effectiveness of capital management within the organization. This metric reflects operational performance and the company's ability to create sustainable value for stakeholders through knowledge, application software, managerial technology, customer interactions, and professional skills, all of which contribute to a competitive market advantage.

Single (2020) also asserts that capital-employed efficiency is a crucial metric for evaluating how well a company uses its capital to generate profits.

Review of Empirical Studies

A review of empirical studies is presented below. The previous empirical studies related to structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency are reviewed and provided in the sub-sections.

Structural Capital Efficiency and Financial Performance

Value is created not by the quantity of goods and services, but by the quality added by employees, such as their knowledge in designing, developing new software programs, or creating new medicines (Ozkan, Cakan & Kayacan, 2017).

Okoye and Okerekeoti (2021) investigated the relationship between structural capital efficiency and economic value added in Nigerian quoted service firms using an ex-post facto research design with a sample of fifty-one companies out of eighty-two listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group (2010-2019). Data were collected from annual reports and financial statements of selected firms, as well as Nigerian Stock Exchange publications. The analysis employed PLS Regression (Panel Least Squares). The study found a significant positive relationship between structural capital efficiency and economic value added at a 5% level of significance. It recommended that firms continue investing in information technology, databases, and training to improve performance.

While the study encompasses a substantial number of companies over a reasonable timeframe, it is essential to recognize that the relationship between structural capital and financial performance can vary significantly across different companies within the service industry. Therefore, the study must incorporate controlled variables to account for differences in size and other moderating variables to have accurate and valid results.

Githaiga et al. (2022) investigated the role of structural capital on the financial performance of microfinance institutions (MFIs). Using a global sample of 444 MFIs from 2013 to 2018, the study analyzed 2,664 MFI-year observations for financial sustainability. Value-added intellectual capital coefficients served as proxies for intellectual capital, while operational self-sufficiency measured financial sustainability. Three-panel data estimation models, fixed effects, random effects, and the dynamic panel system generalized method of moments were used for analysis. The results show that structural capital efficiency negatively impacts financial sustainability.

The above study could be argued in various forms, first, the scope. Using the global scope and sample size seems abstract and cumbersome. The scope shall be specific to address a common phenomenon in one country or a region. Also, the negative effect of structural capital efficiency on financial sustainability could vary significantly across different regions or types of MFIs, potentially limiting the generalization of the findings. Second, the reliance on value-added intellectual capital coefficients might not accurately reflect the true value of structural capital in diverse contexts, especially when other models are considered on a well-defined scope of the study.

Rehman et al. (2022) examined the effect of structural capital and two other components of intellectual capital on the financial performance of Islamic banking. They analyzed data collected from 129 Islamic banks in 29 Muslim countries between 2008 and 2017 using return on assets, return on equity, and Tobin's Q as variables. The results indicate that structural capital efficiency (SCE) has a positive effect on the financial performance of Islamic banks. This study recommends that Islamic banks should focus on the key factors that help sustain a competitive edge and improve bank productivity.

The study mentioned above could be critiqued, particularly regarding its scope, the continents and the demographics of the countries included. Islamic banks operate under different laws, economic conditions, and applications of Sharia, which can influence their acceptability and operations. Therefore, generalizing findings for an entire country may not be accurate without considering other controlled variables that account for these differences. Furthermore, the study did not specify the number of samples collected from each country, which could impact data distribution and, ultimately, the study's findings.

Gurege and Munasinghe (2023) conducted a study to evaluate the effects of structural capital efficiency and various components of intellectual capital on the financial performance of power and energy companies in Sri Lanka. The research employed a combination of quantitative methods and general qualitative analysis. The quantitative portion used the Value-Added Intellectual Coefficient method, which relied on secondary data gathered from a published database of annual reports from the power and energy sectors, covering the years 2011 to 2020. The findings indicate that structural capital efficiency has a positive impact on return on assets and return on equity. However, this effect is not statistically significant for all metrics, including return on assets, return on equity, and asset turnover.

The study mentioned above employed various dependent variables to analyze their impact on the performance of power and energy companies. From an accounting perspective, all these variables are focused on assessing financial performance. However, using three different metrics as dependent variables to evaluate a single objective can create ambiguity and confusion. To address these issues and enhance the clarity of the research, the study should have concentrated on a single accounting metric over a specific period and compared it against other metrics to identify any differences in the outcomes.

Mehmet and Ubaidillah (2023) explored how structural capital efficiency, along with two other aspects of intellectual capital (IC), impacts the financial performance of Islamic Banks in terms of both profitability and productivity. They employed a quantitative methodology with multi-regression analysis to examine the connection between structural capital and the financial performance indicators of Islamic Banks. The analysis utilized data from 49 Islamic Banks covering the period from 2014 to 2018 and incorporated the Modified Value-Added Intellectual Coefficient (MVAIC™), which is a more advanced version of VAIC™. Their analysis reveals that structural capital efficiency does not significantly influence financial performance. In light of their findings, the research recommends investigating other aspects of IC to improve overall performance.

From the above, the time frame (2014 to 2018) may be insufficient to capture lasting trends in the financial performance of Islamic banks. Additionally, structural capital serves as the foundation that connects all other aspects of a company's capital structure. This suggests that a company's success can be assessed by the effectiveness of its operational management structures. Therefore, it is recommended to re-evaluate the data for consistency and to reassess the measurement tool for structural capital to ensure it is adequate and adaptable.

Capital Employed Efficiency and Financial Performance

Capital Employed Efficiency measures how effectively a company utilizes its capital to generate profits. This metric is calculated by comparing a business's profits to the capital employed within that business. It is important because it helps investors and analysts assess how efficiently and effectively a company is investing its capital and at the same time impacting its financial performance.

Mohammad and Mehri (2013) examined the relationship between capital-employed efficiency and operating cash flow (financial performance metric). They gathered data from a sample of 161 companies in the Tehran Stock Exchange during the period 2008-2012. By utilizing linear regression to assess the relationship, the findings indicated a significant and positive correlation between capital employed efficiency and operational

cash flow. The study recommends that increasing the amount of value added based on capital employed leads to the generation of more cash flow from operations.

Based on the above study, it can be argued that the time frame for data observation is insufficient for achieving accurate results. A longer observation period would enhance the ability to analyze data characteristics effectively and obtain more reliable outcomes. Therefore, it is advisable to extend the duration to allow for a thorough analysis.

Okoye et al. (2021) conducted a study to examine the relationship between capital employed efficiency and the two other components of intellectual capital and economic value added of quoted service firms in Nigeria from 2010 to 2019. The ex-post facto research design was used on the fifty-one (51) sampled firms, using secondary data from their annual reports analyzed via E-Views 10.0. The analysis included Pearson correlation, a heteroskedasticity test, and panel least squares (PLS) regression. The findings revealed a significant positive relationship between capital employed efficiency and Economic Value Added at a 5% significance level.

Similarly, Yerisma et al. (2021) examined the impact of capital employed efficiency and two other components of intellectual capital on the financial performance of the consumer goods industry sector in Nigeria. The return on equity (ROE) was used as a proxy for the dependent variable. The research focused on all consumer goods industries listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for the period 2015-2019, with a sample of 31 companies selected using purposive sampling. The study employed panel data regression with a fixed effect model using the EViews 9 program for data processing. The findings of the study indicate that capital-employed efficiency has a positive and significant influence on the financial performance of consumer goods in Indonesia.

Arumana et al. (2022) conducted a study on non-financial companies listed on the Nigeria Exchange Group to investigate how capital employed and structural capital efficiency impact financial performance. The study analyzed 75 firms from a population of 85, using data from 2012 to 2021. Panel regression analysis was conducted, revealing that capital employed efficiency (CEE) positively and significantly affects financial performance, as measured by return on assets (ROA). The study recommends that firms increase capital employed to improve performance. These findings align with Firer & Williams (2003), which emphasized the importance of physical capital for corporate performance in South Africa.

Lodikero & Soyinka (2023) conducted a study on the impact of financial management practices on the success of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The research compared the return on equity of 40 listed manufacturing companies with the effects of financial management practices, focusing on working capital practices, capital structure practices, and corporate governance practices. The study utilized a correlational research design and relied on corporate annual reports and websites from 2017 to 2021 as the primary sources of secondary data. The study revealed a strong correlation between these practices and business performance as measured by return on equity (ROE). It recommended that Nigerian manufacturing companies ensure the consistent maintenance of these practices in all aspects of organizational decision-making to enhance their performance.

The research conducted by Barak & Rakesh (2023) examined the influence of capital-employed efficiency on the financial performance of Indian private-sector banks. They gathered annual financial reports from 17 banks spanning the years 2010 to 2021. Using the modified value-added intellectual coefficient (MVAIC) methodology, they evaluated the impact of capital-employed efficiency on financial performance. The results indicate that capital-employed efficiency has a statistically significant effect on the financial performance of private sector banks in India.

Theoretical Review

This study examines how the efficiency of structural organization and capital employed influences financial performance, which can be understood through the lens of the Resource-Based Theory (RBT). According to RBT, firms with well-structured systems and efficient use of capital can leverage these resources to create value and achieve sustained competitive advantage. As such, the research explores how these resources, being rare and valuable, contribute to the superior financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Okumoko et al. (2021) point out that the resource-based theory is centered on the idea that a business's uniqueness is derived from its specific combination of resources, forming the foundation of its competitive

advantage. Throughout the history of strategic management, the main objective has been to understand the factors behind the differing performances of businesses in the same industry (Porter, 1980). In light of this, the variables used in the study can be linked with the tenets of RBT for a proper understanding of the theory and how it supports the study to achieve the objectives and solve the research problem.

In the context of RBT, the structure of an organization is a valuable and unique resource. An efficient structure could be a source of competitive advantage as it may allow firms to reduce costs and improve decision-making. A well-structured organization ensures optimal use of resources, which aligns with RBT's focus on efficiently utilizing resources to gain superior performance. This means that the structure of a firm rooted in industry operations or ownership of particular resources and competencies can lead to improved performance (Barney, 1991).

Equally, the RBT argue that the firm's capital resources (such as financial capital, physical assets, and human capital) can be sources of competitive advantage. Therefore, the efficient use of capital enables firms to maximize returns while minimizing wastage, which directly relates to financial performance. RBT emphasizes that firms with rare and hard-to-imitate capital resources are more likely to achieve sustained superior performance. This can be linked to how capital-employed efficiency affects financial outcomes, as firms that effectively deploy their capital may create value in ways that competitors find hard to replicate. Therefore, the resource-based theory offers a strong framework for this investigation, such that a company can outperform its competitors by utilizing a competitive advantage, whether through industry-specific operations or access to specific resources and skills (Barney, 1991).

Financial Performance: From an RBT perspective, financial performance is the outcome of how well a firm uses its valuable resources (e.g., human capital, structural capital, relational capital, physical assets, or other financial resources). Firms that have developed unique capabilities (such as efficient capital deployment and an effective organizational structure) are more likely to achieve superior financial performance.

Significant progress has been made in resource-based theory over the last thirty years (Jay et al., 2021). The efficacy of financial performance in an organization, including manufacturing firms, cannot be denied since economic value is generated when customers are willing to pay more for a company's products or services than the cost incurred to produce them (Brandenburger & Stuart, 1996).

Therefore, RBT elucidates that organizations can achieve superior performance by effectively utilizing their resources in the market. It is on this premise that this study adopted the resource-based theory to explain the characteristics of structural and capital-employed efficiency and financial performance. Resource-based theory (RBT) is based on the concept of economic rent and views a company as a combination of capabilities. In line with RBT, structural and capital-employed efficiency is seen to enhance competitive advantage for companies. Consequently, this study suggests that the effect of structural and capital-employed efficiency can increase the value of listed manufacturing firms and achieve long-term performance benefits through process improvement, increased productivity, employee dedication, promotion of a positive work environment, and investment in physical assets as advocated by the theory.

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employed an ex-post facto research design to investigate the effect of structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency on the financial performance of listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria. The data is collected from published annual reports of the sampled companies. This study used panel data that covered 2013 to 2023 and utilized purposive sampling techniques to select a sample size of twelve (12) from a population of twenty-one (21) listed consumer goods firms in Nigeria based on the available data presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Population of the Study and Sample Size

Company	Sampled	Date Listed	Date Incorporated
BUA FOODS PLC		2022	2005
CADBURY NIGERIA PLC.	√	1976	1965

CHAMPION BREW. PLC. [BLS]	√	1983	1974
DANGOTE SUGAR REFINERY PLC [CG+]	√	2007	2005
DN TYRE & RUBBER PLC [DIP]		-	1961
GOLDEN GUINEA BREW. PLC. [BLS]		-	1962
GUINNESS NIG PLC [CG+]	√	1965	1950
HONEYWELL FLOUR MILL PLC [BLS][CG+]	√	2009	1985
INTERNATIONAL BREWERIES PLC. [BLS]		1971	1971
MCNICHOLS PLC		2009	2004
MULTI-TREX INTEGRATED FOODS PLC [DWL]		2010	1999
N NIG. FLOUR MILLS PLC.	√	1972	1971
NASCON ALLIED INDUSTRIES PLC		1992	1973
NESTLE NIGERIA PLC. [CG+]	√	1979	1969
NIGERIAN BREW. PLC. [CG+]	√	1973	1946
NIGERIAN ENAMELWARE PLC.		1979	1960
P Z CUSSONS NIGERIA PLC. [CG+]	√	1972	1948
UNILEVER NIGERIA PLC. [CG+]	√	1973	1923
UNION DICON SALT PLC. [DWL]	√	1993	1991
VITAFOAM NIG PLC.	√	1978	1962

Source: Field Survey, 2025

The study used descriptive statistics to explain the characteristics of the variable and employed feasible generalized regression technique to analyze the panel data through STATA 13. This study adopts the model of Enekwe et al. (2022) stated as $ROA_{ij} = \beta_0 + \beta_1HCE_{ij} + \beta_2SCE_{ij} + \beta_3CCE_{ij} + Ut$

To achieve the objectives of the study, the model was revised to better align with these goals and is expressed as follows: $ROA = \alpha + \beta_1SCEE_{it} + \beta_2CEE_{it} + \epsilon_i$

Where: ROA = Return on Assets; SCE = Structural Capital Efficiency; CEE = Capital Employed Efficiency, β_1 - β_2 = Coefficients of determination; α = Intercept of the regression line; it = firm at time t; ϵ_i = Residual or error term. The variables definitions, measurements, and sources are presented below in Table 2.

Table 2: Variable Definitions, Measurements, and Sources

Variable Definitions	Measurement	Sources
Return on Assets (ROA) is a financial metric that measures how efficiently a company uses its assets to generate profit.	The ratio of the profit after tax to total assets (PAT/TA)	Enekwe et al. (2022)
Value-added (VA) represents the wealth or economic value a company creates through its resources. Measures a firm's efficiency in utilizing intellectual capital, human capital, and structural capital to generate value and competitive advantage.	Operating Profit (OP) + Employee cost (EC) + Depreciation (D) + Amortization (A)	Enekwe et al. (2022)
Structural Capital Efficiency (SCE) is a measure of how efficiently a company utilizes its	SC is derived by subtracting Human Capital (HC) from	Arumana et al. (2022)

structural capital (SC) to generate value. Structural capital includes processes, databases, organizational culture, patents, and other non-human assets that support business operations	VA. Where SCE is calculated as SC divided by Value Added (VA)		
Capital Employed Efficiency (CEE) is a measure of how efficiently a company utilizes its physical and financial capital to generate value.	CEE is calculated as Value Added (VA) divided by Capital Employed (CE), where CE represents total assets minus intangible assets.		Arumana et al. (2022)

Source: Field Survey, 2025

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents and discusses the results of the panel data analysis of this study. Table 3 presents the descriptive statistics results which explain the characteristics of the variables used in the study.

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ROA	132	.066	.091	-.30	.37
SCE	132	.569	.449	-2.55	.94
CEE	132	.432	.417	-3.04	1.55

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 3 shows an average 6.6% return on assets. The profitability disparities between consumer goods firms in Nigeria become apparent because ROA measurements span between -30% and 37%. The sector exhibits high operational and financial management differences, which result in a 9.1% standard deviation of ROA. In addition, most of the firms use 56.9% of their corporate resources to produce profitability. Some companies achieve effective structural capital utilization through their internal processes and strategies, but several others demonstrate less efficiency in SC implementation, ranging from -2.55 up to 0.94.

The moderate standard deviation of 44.9% underscores the uneven distribution of structural capital efficiency among the firms. Finally, the average capital employed efficiency for the dataset reaches 43.2%. This means, on average, consumer goods use 43.2% of their financial capital to achieve profitability. Equally, the minimum and maximum values of capital employed efficiency range from -3.04 to 1.55, which indicated that some companies were effectively managing the resources injected into the business while others were not. The wide delta of 41.7 further supports that there was a wide range between the minimum and maximum values of the injected capital.

To further explain the characteristics of the data, the study employs a pairwise correlation to look at all possible combinations of variables in a dataset, generating a matrix of correlations. This is necessary to calculate the correlation of every pair of variables in the dataset to identify potential associations that might warrant further investigation. A pairwise correlation interprets the strength and direction of the linear relationship. Thus, a pairwise correlation refers to the correlation calculated between every possible pair of variables within a dataset as against the Pearson correlation that calculates the linear relationship between just two variables. The results of the calculated values of pairwise correlation are presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4 analyzes the relationship between return on assets (ROA), capital employed efficiency (CEE), and structural capital efficiency. The data reveals that SCE has a statistically significant positive correlation of 0.329 with ROA, indicating a moderate association between these variables. It elucidates that consumer goods companies that optimize processes and cherish good corporate culture will record higher profitability and, ultimately, a healthy financial performance.

Furthermore, Capital Employed Efficiency, with the calculated values of 0.540 at the 1% significant level, shows a significant positive correlation with ROA. This finding highlights the importance of SCE as a vital component in driving the profitability of consumer goods. Firms.

Table 4a: Pairwise correlations

Variables	ROA	SCE	CEE
ROA	1.000		
SCE	0.329*	1.000	
	(0.000)		
CEE	0.540*	0.213*	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.014)	
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1			

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Finally, the relationship between SCE and CEE shows a relatively weak association, with a coefficient of 0.213, which is also significant at the 1% level. This value is substantially lower than the commonly accepted threshold of 0.85 for multicollinearity, indicating that the independent variables do not exhibit strong interdependence. Consequently, this lack of multicollinearity supports the validity of the individual contributions of SCE and CEE to ROA, allowing for more robust insights into how they uniquely affect a firm's financial success.

Despite the lack of the presence of multicollinearity from the pairwise correlation, the study executed a robustness test to provide a quality assurance method to check if the model's results are stable when assumptions are not met. Therefore, the variance inflation factor and tolerance numbers have been calculated to guide the study provided below in Table 4b.

Table 4b: Robustness Test

	VIF	1/VIF
CEE	1.047	.955
SCE	1.047	.955
Mean VIF	1.047	
Hetttest	0.0059	
Hausman Specification Test	0.6206	
Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier Test for Random Effects	0.0001	

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 4 presented the multicollinearity results, which suggested that the variables in the study did not have any problems with multicollinearity. Tolerance values more than 0.10 and VIF values less than 10 generally serve as indicators of this (Gujarati & Porter, 2009). This was consistent with the assumption made by the standard regression model, which stated that the independent variables in the model should not be closely related to one another. This provides essential evidence about the reliability of the regression model through robustness testing. The Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) has a mean of 1.047, and its corresponding 1/VIF is 0.955. These values demonstrate that multicollinearity does not affect the model because they remain below the specified thresholds of 10 and 1, respectively. The data demonstrates that adding these two independent variables will not affect the accuracy of the analysis outcome, as there is no presence of multicollinearity.

The results of the heteroskedasticity test (hetttest) have shown a calculated p-value of 0.0059 at a 1% significance level. This suggests that heteroskedasticity is present in the model, meaning the error terms do not

have constant variances since the p-value is less than 0.05. It is important to address heteroskedasticity to ensure that statistically significant variables do not appear insignificant.

The Hausman specification test was conducted to determine whether random effects or a fixed effect estimator is more appropriate for panel data analysis. The results of the Hausman Specification Test show a p-value of 0.6206, which is greater than 0.05, so we choose the random effects model. Using the random effect result was contingent upon the results of the Lagrangian multiplier test such that the pooled OLS regression will be employed if the result was not significant, otherwise, and the random effect will be applied. The Breusch and Pagan Lagrangian Multiplier (LM) test for random effects demonstrates significant statistical importance through its small p-value of 0.0001. The outcomes demand the random effects model rather than the pooled OLS model because the random effects model considers factors that specifically affect individual firms. However, to settle the issue of heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, this study utilized Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) regression, as it is appropriate when the assumptions of ordinary least squares (OLS) regression are violated, particularly in cases of heteroscedasticity or autocorrelation.

The results of the Feasible Generalized Least Squares (FGLS) are presented in Table 5 below. The Wald chi-square test indicates whether a specific coefficient is significantly different from zero, meaning that the variable has a statistically meaningful effect on the outcome.

Table 5: Cross-Sectional Time-Series FGLS Regression

ROA	Coef.	St. Err.	t-value	p-value			
SCE	.045	.015	3.10	.002***			
CEE	.107	.016	6.80	0.000***			
Constant	-.006	.012	-0.56	0.578			
Number of Obs	132		Wald chi-square	67.945			
Prob > chi2	0.000						
*** p<.01, ** p<.05, * p<.1							

Source: STATA 13, 2025

Table 5 indicates the Wald chi-square statistic test result for the combined effect of structural and capital employed efficiency of 67.945 with a p-value of 0.000 at a 1% significance level. Since the Wald chi-square value is large and the p-value is very low (less than 0.05), this implies a significant combined effect of the independent variables on ROA. Therefore, structural capital efficiency (SCE) positively and significantly affects return on assets (ROA) with a coefficient value of 0.045 and a p-value of 0.002, which demonstrates that firms' structural capital efficiency has a positive effect on the financial performance of listed consumer goods in Nigeria.

The results support the rejection of the null hypothesis that SCE has no significant effect on the financial performance of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. The finding affirms that SCE has a significant effect on the financial performance of listed consumer goods in Nigeria. This finding aligns with the previous study conducted by Okoye and Okerekeoti (2021), Rehman et al. (2022) and Gurege and Munasinghe (2023)

Similarly, CEE has a coefficient value of 0.107 and a p-value of 0.000, signifying that CEE has a significant positive effect on the financial performance of consumer goods. The null hypothesis fails because CEE demonstrates strong significance; this hypothesis, which assumes that capital-employed efficiency has no significant effect on financial performance, is rejected. The result, therefore, affirms that CEE has a significant effect on the financial performance of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, and this finding aligns with the past studies conducted by Mohammad and Mehri (2013), Okoye et al. (2021) and Yerisma et al. (2021).

V. CONCLUSION

After conducting the hypothesis test, the study concluded that both structural capital efficiency and capital employed efficiency positively affect the financial performance of listed consumer goods companies in Nigeria.

These findings emanate from the Resource-Based Theory (RBT) framework, which posits that companies achieve greater profitability through effective resource management and individual uniqueness in strategic approaches. This involves strategically aligning the organizational structure with the company's objectives and employing an optimal mix of tangible and intangible assets to ensure efficient resource management. The study further recommends the following:

1. Consumer goods companies should prioritize the enhancement of their structural capital by actively promoting corporate culture, internal workflows, ethical conducts, technology adoptions, automation and effectively utilizing organizational structure to enhance positive work environment and individual innovations. Moreover, operational excellence and sustainable financial growth are anchored in comprehensive training initiatives that equip employees with the necessary skills. Also, the strategic implementation of advanced technologies to streamline processes and continuous improvements in operational procedures require very active management and leadership commitment with clear board mandates towards the strategic direction of the company. These efforts collectively bolster the organization's operational capabilities, resulting in improved efficiency, productivity, and ultimately, stronger financial performance. Moreover, fostering a culture of knowledge sharing and collaboration can significantly amplify these benefits, driving the company toward long-term financial growth and profitability.
2. Consumer goods Firms must develop robust financial management structures aimed at enhancing the efficiency of their capital investments. This involves implementing strategic frameworks that prioritize effective capital deployment, ensuring that necessary investments are made while minimizing idle capital. Additionally, organizations should utilize comprehensive performance monitoring tools that track the utilization of financial resources. These tools not only facilitate informed decision-making but also ensure that allocated funds contribute significantly to driving profitability and fostering sustainable growth. By establishing these practices, firms can optimize their financial resources, enabling them to respond swiftly to market changes and seize new opportunities with confidence to drive profitability.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Abdirahman, A. A., & Tarique, K. (2020). The role of structural and capital efficiencies in enhancing the financial performance of manufacturing firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Business, Economics & Management*, 3(2), 35-47.
- [2] Adelekan, S., Erigbe, P., Ojo, J., & Toriola, Anu. (2019). Knowledge management and manufacturing firms' performance in Nigeria. [Paper presentation] Department of Business Management, Mountain Top University, Ogun State.
- [3] Alavi, M., & Leidner, D., E. (2001). Knowledge management and knowledge management system: Conceptual Foundations and Research Issues, *MIS Quarterly Review*, 25(1), 107-136.
- [4] Al-Omouh, K., Palacios-Marqués, D., & Ulrich, K. (2022). The impact of intellectual capital on supply chain agility and collaborative knowledge creation in responding to unprecedented pandemic crises. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*. 178(2), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121603>.
- [5] Andreeva, T., & Garanina, T. (2016). Do all elements of intellectual capital matter for organisational performance? Evidence from Russian context. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 17(2), 397-412.
- [6] Arumana, J. O., Daniel, E. & Enomate, B. (2022). Capital employed and structural capital efficiency and financial performance of listed non-financial companies in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities Social Science and Management*, 2(5), 24-341.
- [7] Asutay, M. & Ubaidillah. (2023). Examining the impact of intellectual capital performance on financial performance in Islamic banks. *Journal of the Knowledge Economy*, 1(33), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13132-023-01114-1>
- [8] Aziz, U, R., Ejaz, A., & Anam, I. (2022). Intellectual capital efficiency and performance: Evidence from Islamic Banks. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 22(1), 113-121, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2021.02.004>.
- [9] Bailoa, P. (2017). Transition to a knowledge-based economy: Leveraging Intangible Assets for Competitive Advantage. *International Journal of Economic Development*, 6(4), 89-101.
- [10] Demir, A., Budur, T., Hiwa, M., & Heshmati, A. (2021). Links between Knowledge Management and Organizational Sustainability: Does the ISO 9001 certification have an effect? *Knowledge Management*

- Research & Practice <https://doi/10.1080/14778238.2020.1860663>
- [11] Elisabeth, A., Fabienne, Berger-Remy. (2019). Intellectual Capital and Financial Performance: A Meta-Analysis and Research Agenda, 22(1), 216 - 249. <https://hal.science/hal-02139763>
- [12] Enekwe, C. I., Udeh, S. N., & Okwo, I., M. (2022). Effect of Intellectual Capital on Financial Performance of Listed Consumer Goods Companies in Nigeria. *European Journal of Accounting, Finance and Investment*, 8(6), 10-26.
- [13] Firer, S., & Williams, S. M. (2003). Intellectual capital and traditional measures of corporate performance. *Journal of Intellectual Capital*, 4(3), 348-360, <https://doi.org/10.1108/14691930310487806>
- [14] Githaiga, N., Soi, N., & Buigut, K. (2022). Does intellectual capital matter to MFIs' financial sustainability? *Asian Journal of Accounting Research*. 8(1), <https://doi/10.1108/AJAR-06-2021-0080>.
- [15] Guruge, N. H., & Munasinghe, A. (2023). Influence of intellectual capital on the financial performance of power & energy sector companies in Sri Lanka. *Proceedings of 13th International Conference on Business & Information, 2022* <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4434862>
- [16] Hassani, M., & Misaghi, M. (2013). A study on the relationship between capital employed efficiency and operating cash flow: Evidence from Tehran Stock Exchange. *Management Science Letters*, 3(1), 1089-1094.
- [17] Helin, G. Y., Daniel, T. H., M. & Fitria, H. (2018). Relationship between value-added capital employed, value-added human capital, structural capital value added and financial performance: *Investment Management and Financial Innovations*, 15(2), 222-231, <http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/imfi>.
- [18] Jarrett, J. (2019). Valuing intangible assets and financial reporting. *International Journal of Current Research in Medical Sciences*, 1(2), 63-74. <http://ijrcms.com/link.php?id=12>
- [19] Lodikero, O., & Soyinka K. A. (2023). Financial Management Practices and the Performance of Listed Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. *African Journal of Accounting and Financial Research* 6(3), 81-97, <https://doi/10.52589/AJAFR-ulhtxgcc>
- [20] Nwamaka, J. F., & Ezekwesili, T. P., U. (2021). Capital employed efficiency and Economic value added of quoted companies. *International Journal of Research*, 8(10).
- [21] Okoye, N. J. F., & Okerekeoti, C., U. (2021). Structural capital efficiency and economic value added of quoted service firms in Nigeria. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 1(10), 2782-7658, www.ijaar.org. <https://doi/10.46654>.
- [22] Okoye, N. J., Ifurueze, M. S., Agubata, N. S., Emeka-Nwokeji, N. (2021). Intellectual Capital and Economic Value Added of Quoted Service Firms in Nigeria. *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd)*, ISSN:2456-6470, 5(2), 382-391. <https://www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd38442.pdf>
- [23] Okoye, N., & Okerekeoti, C. (2021). Structural Capital Efficiency and Economic Value Added of Quoted Service Firms In Nigeria. 1, 2782-7658.
- [24] Okumoko, T., Cookey, I., & Mcdonald, Q. (2021). Intangible Assets and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Empirical Investigation. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*. 74-84, <https://doi/10.9734/ajeba/2021/v21i1130443>.
- [25] Olaoye, C. O., & Adesina, O., D. (2022). Capital Structure and Financial Performance of Manufacturing Companies in Nigeria. *Journal of Applied and Theoretical Social Sciences*, 4(4), 471- 491, <https://doi.org/10.37241/jatss.2022.78>
- [26] Ozkan, N., Cakan, S., & Kayacan, M. (2017). Intellectual capital and financial performance: A study of the Turkish Banking Sector. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 17(3), 190-198.
- [27] Yerisma, W., Arfan I., & Chandra, S. (2021). The effect of capital employed, human capital and structural capital on the financial performance of the consumer goods sector from 2015-2019. *International journal of trends in accounting research*, 2(1).
- [28] Zangouinezhad, A., & Moshabaki, A. (2009). The role of structural capital on competitive intelligence. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*. 109(2), 262-280, <https://doi/10.1108/02635570910930136>.